

Open Source Platform for Scalable Multi-Purpose Virtual Desktop Infrastructures

NFDI4
BIOIMAGE

Michael Scherle¹, Rafael Gieschke¹, Isabela Denisa Mocanu¹,
Björn Grüning², Dirk von Suchodoletz¹

¹ eScience Department, Computer Center University of Freiburg, Germany

² Chair of Bioinformatics, University of Freiburg, Germany

Open Source Virtual Desktop Infrastructure (OSVDI)

<https://gitlab.uni-freiburg.de/opensourcevdi>

- Free and open source software
- Cloud-independent
- Join our new community :)

SPICE/QEMU Remote Access

- Robust remote sessions during guest life-cycle
- (Restricted) access to sensitive data for visualization with isolated guest system
- Enhanced and secured access, e.g., to software, data visualization, or (sensitive) data

Demo

<https://demo.osvdi.uni-freiburg.de>
User: user1 / Password: pass1

Enhance different VDI research use cases

- **Interactive** remote workstations (virtual machines)
- Use any existing (Windows/Linux) software
- Remote processing and visualization
- Scales with large data volume
- Centrally located licensed software
- Flexible environment provisioning and sharing
- e.g., for remote training, evaluation, replication
- Centrally located data management

GPU hardware acceleration

- Full GPU hardware feature support
- e.g., 3D rendering, video-stream encoding, or AI
- GPU virtualization/partitioning via SR-IOV
- Fixed or dynamic time-sliced partitioning
- Over-provisioning of GPU time possible
- Fixed VRAM allocation

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